
Multidimensional Perspectives on Child and Adolescent Development: A Review of Major Theories and Principles

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ABSTRACT: Development is defined as the gradual process of strengthening the physical capability, cognitive competencies, emotional self-regulation, interpersonal relationships, and moral reasoning. An individual's holistic development is constructed through interaction of physiological factors, immediate environment, and life experiences. The present study aims to discuss child and adolescent development as distinguishable yet interdependent stages, signifying the developmental characteristics of childhood and the observable changes in all the domains of development that occur during adolescence. Key principles development are clarified to explain patterns of growth and individual differences. Major theories of development were investigated to provide theoretical grounding and methodical understanding of how personality, cognition, social behavior, and moral reasoning develop over time. Overall, the study offers a basic association for understanding child and adolescent development from all perspective.

KEYWORDS: development, child development, adolescent development, principles of development, theories of development

INTRODUCTION

Development is an ongoing process by which an individual develops and progresses more in every domain of life. It includes the development of abilities, knowledge, attitudes, behavior and emotional maturity which permit an individual to perceive themselves better and contribute to community. Individual's life experiences, education, environment, culture and self-determination all influences an individual's holistic development throughout life.

World Health Organization (WHO) defines, development as a broad life-long continuous process of learning new skills and promoting overall well-being. It highlights positive improvements in all aspects of development which are significantly important in early childhood for establishing the groundwork for subsequent productivity, learning, mental processes and physical health.

Development has broadened over time to include improvements in quality of life such as income, wealth, health, knowledge, capabilities, freedoms and self-esteem, not just economic growth but also socio-political dimensions that expand people's real freedoms and choices (Semasinghe, 2020). From the perspective of Psychology, development is the sequence of growth and change that an individual experiences during the period of their lifespan. It includes changes in one's cognitive, emotional and social dynamics that influences how an individual perceives, behaves, understand and interpret the surroundings.

Systematic changes in mental traits and experiences that people go through throughout their lives is a result of ongoing interactions with their surroundings and situations (Chopik, 2022). Psychological development begins at conception and continues throughout different stages of life from birth till old age, focusing on how changes take place throughout the different phases of individual's life and role of distinct domains for nurturing the individual's psychological processes.

Laura Berk explained the five periods of development which are supported by many theories in her book "Child Development" which began from prenatal period which last from conception till birth, infancy and toddlerhood period which last from birth till 2 years, early childhood which last from 2 years till 6 years, middle childhood which last from 6 years till 11 years and adolescence which last from 11 years to 12 years (Berk, 2015).

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PERIOD OF DEVELOPMENT	AGE
Prenatal Period	Conception to Birth
Infancy and Toddlerhood	Birth to 2 Years
Early Childhood	2 to 6 Years
Middle Childhood	6 to 11 Years
Adolescence	11 to 18 Years

Figure 1. Periods of Development from Prenatal to Adolescence

This study will specifically articulate about Child and Adolescent Development. Child Development is an ongoing process through which an individual evolves from birth to adolescence. Childhood Development begins from 2 years and lasting up to 11 years, laying emphasis on the development of multiple dimensions of the individual. As the child develops, they learn how to master motor skills, perceive stimulus, communicate, comprehend and interact with their surroundings. Psychological development during childhood refers to the process which involves development of child's mind, sensory perceptual abilities, emotional, social and personality development. It explores how a child develops thinking, recognize, recall, and express their emotions.

Developmental psychologists define child development as a process of change in which children gradually acquire physical, cognitive, emotional, and social skills and competencies through both ongoing and irregular processes throughout the early years, becoming more skilful at what they do (Yi and Keat, 2024) . Child gradually develops the foundation of self- confidence, ability to recognize between things which are morally correct or not, acquire personality traits and enhance their interpersonal skills during this developmental phase. A child's psychological growth is directly influenced by their family functioning, childhood experiences and social environment.

Adolescence Development is the period between childhood and adulthood lasting from 12 years to 18 years. It is marked as one of the most significant developmental periods of an individual life where the body goes through puberty related growth and sexual development. In this stage individual experiences major physical, emotional, cognitive and social changes.

Adolescent development as the stage of life that starts with puberty and is characterized by major biological, cognitive, psychosocial, and emotional changes that help people transition from childhood to adulthood and develop their sense of self (Families et al., 2019). Adolescent development is not just associated with puberty but also with the dramatic changes in all domains of development and social relationships. These transitions take place in the surroundings of family, peers and cultural. In this phase the individual has more intense emotions as compared to child, they feel more independent and develop a clear sense of their identity (Steinberg and Morris, 2001). Friendship and peer groups play a major role in this phase influencing how an individual establishes and maintains meaningful social and romantic relationships.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Despite in depth research in child and adolescent development, available literature mainly focuses on individual theories, leading to a fragmented understanding of developmental processes. There is a lack of comprehensive reviews that critically combine and compare major theoretical perspectives. Current studies often emphasize descriptive explanations rather than critical evaluation of strengths, limitations, and practical relevance. Furthermore, limited attention has been given to how these theories collectively explain the multidimensional and dynamic nature of development. Therefore, there is a need for a systematic and analytical review that synthesizes foundational principles and theories. Such an approach can provide a more holistic understanding of development. It also helps in identifying gaps in theory application. This review aims to address these limitations and offer an integrated perspective.

Objectives of The Study

- 2.1 To critically evaluate the child and adolescent development.
- 2.2 To analyze the basic principles of development.
- 2.3 To review theories of development and their role in establishing groundwork of individual development.

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PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT

The Principles of Development explain the patterns that direct human development. By understanding these principles, we can better comprehend how and why individual develops differently, how their experiences influence their developmental process and how it continues throughout their life. Core principles of development include the following-

Figure 2. Principles of Development

- 1. Nature-Nurture:** - It is one of the most fundamental principles of development which is based on the concept of interaction between nature and nurture, where nature is defined as an individual's biological traits from their parents including their genetic makeup, physical features and innate abilities; on the other hand, nurture refers to the environmental factors that influences development such as family, culture, education and social experiences. Development is a result of gene-environment interplay, where biological predispositions and experiential factors jointly shape cognitive, emotional, and social outcomes (Dodge, 2004). Development is the outcome of conscious reciprocation between nature and nurture rather than being exclusively dependent on a single component.
- 2. Continuity-Discontinuity:** - Development can also studied through the framework of continuity and discontinuity, which explains the process of change over time. It involves both continuous and discontinuous models, confiding on the particular characteristic which is under study. Cohering to the continuity principle, development is considered to be a gradual and cumulative process which implies change happens through a series of systematic steps based on past experiences on the other hand discontinuity suggests that development happens in independent phases with observable changes that derivate from early experiences (Sternberg and Okagaki, 1989). These phases are often associated with significant behavioral changes and other changes such as concrete thinking patterns in childhood to abstract thinking patterns in adolescence. Both continuity and discontinuity are present throughout individual's growth, where some areas of development progress hierarchically while other have specific phase to develop.
- 3. Stability-Instability:** - The principle of stability and instability concentrates on the amount to which individual characteristics change or remain constant through lifespan. Development can together include both growth as well as infrangible individual patterns, revealing the importance of ascertaining both change and consistency over lifespan (Bornstein et al., (2017). Stability denotes enduring individual characteristics that persists across the lifespan, whereas instability refers to developmental changes influenced by various factors and major life events. Some areas are changeable while other exhibit long term consistency. Understanding stability and instability highlights the importance of experience and life- long edification while also benefiting in understanding individual differences.
- 4. Development Is Multi-Dimensional and Multi-Directional:** - Development is multi- dimensional which means it is not accomplished in a single dimension but rather in multiple dimensions. These dimensions include physical, cognitive, emotional, social and moral development. Although each dimension develops at a distinct manner but they all are interconnected and a change in one dimension frequently influences the other dimension. This demonstrates the importance of considering development as holistic rather than focusing on single factor. Development is multi-directional because different skills develop at different leap of life and in distinct ways. Over time, some abilities may grow, some may diminish, and some may undergo quality changes. Principles multidimensional and multidirectional are central tenets of life-span developmental psychology. Research shows that human development involves multiple interacting processes that can change in various directions across different domains over time (Infurna, 2021).
- 5. Development Is Life Long:** - According to this principle development continues throughout the lifespan. Every stage of life involves growth and change, like as adults we engage into new responsibilities and grow intellectually, emotionally and socially

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while in later life we develop wisdom and emotional control which is the reflection of our previous life events. Individuals consistently accommodate their cognitive approaches to recondition functioning and reward for age-related transformations, illustrating that human development is lifelong. It proclaims that each stage of life has stage specific developmental tasks and significance (Baltes et al., 1999).

A study conducted by Black et al., (2016) examined the key principles of early human development across the life course, according to this study, development is an ongoing and cumulative process in which early experiences have a significant impact on later results. The study also made clear that both biological, psychological and environmental factors have an impact on developmental processes. It came to the conclusion that comprehending development requires a comprehensive and integrated approach as opposed to a limited focus on discrete domains. Another study conducted by Prinzie et al., (2019) on principles of development stated that, individual differences result from variances in environmental and cultural circumstances, yet development follows a basic path. It highlighted the constant interaction between genetic and environmental elements during the developmental process.

THEROIES OF DEVELOPMENT

Developmental theories support the methodical understanding of how and why people go through evolutions across different phase of their life. The theories discussed in this study demonstrates patterns of growth in personality, cognition, social behavior, and moral reasoning, offering critical perceptions about development. By cross examining theoretical viewpoints, psychologists can interpret developmental changes in relation to biological evolution, social experiences, and environmental influences. Theories also helps in establishing observations of human development into meaningful concepts.

1. Psychosexual Theory of Development: -

Sigmund Freud, the innovator of psychoanalysis, proposed the psychosexual theory to elaborate development of personality from infancy through adulthood. According to him, personality is formed through unconscious desires and conflicts that are the surface for manifestation of sexual energy known as libido. He believed that early childhood experiences play a crucial role in the development of individual personality once they grow up, and that unresolved conflicts in any stage can result in behavioural or emotional difficulties later in life. He described personality as combination of three interacting structures: the Id, Ego, and Superego.

Figure 3. Structure of Personality

The Id is the most crucial part of personality following the pleasure principle, it is present from birth, and activates entirely in the unconscious. The Ego emerges as the child develops, operating according to the reality principle. It serves as an intermediate between the reactive needs of the Id and the barriers from external environment, enabling the individual to respond in socially desirable ways while gratifying their basic needs. The Superego represents internalized moral values, and ideals which are active on the moral principle. It aims for perfection and modulates feelings of guilt or shame when social rules are ruptured. When these structures are in conflict, the ego uses various defence mechanisms to regulate anxiety and maintain psychological equilibrium (Berliana, 2025). This theory of development focuses on sexual energy which is concentrated on various erogenous zones during personality development. While unresolved disputes can lead to fixation and affect adult behaviour, successful conflict resolution at every stage promotes healthy personality development (Elkatawneh, 2013). According to this theory there are 5 stages of development-

❖ **Oral stage:** - It occurs from birth to around one year. At this stage the infant's driven energy is directed towards mouth, and actions such as sucking, biting, and chewing give satisfaction. The infant counts on caregivers for support and consolation. This

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stage is pivotal for the formation of trust and security. If the child is exposed to excesses of gratification or frustration during this stage, it leads to fixation, leading to traits such as intense dependency, overeating, smoking, nail-biting, and an inclination to seek comfort through oral means in adulthood.

❖ **Anal stage:** - It extends over one to three years, with concentration on bowel and bladder control. During this, the child passes through toilet training, learning self-control and independence. The Role of parents in training is strongly influential to understand personality development. Highly strict toilet training may lead to an anal-retentive personality, with personality such as orderliness, stubbornness, or perfectionism whereas very lenient training may lead to an anal-expulsive personality, with personality such as messiness, disorganization, or rebelliousness.

❖ **Phallic stage:** - This stage last from three to six years, where child's focus shifting onto the genitals. Children perceive sexual differences and establish relationships with the opposite parent, developing what Freud termed as Oedipus complex in boys which means love and attraction towards mothers and the Electra complex in girls which means there love and attraction towards father. Successful resolution of these complexes results in personality like optimistic and better emotional regulation whereas fixation may lead to challenges with authority, unstable relationships, or sexual dysfunction in late adulthood.

❖ **Latency stage:** - Latency lasts from six years to puberty where sexual impulses are inhibited. The libido is reoriented towards learning, building friendships and interests, as well as competencies. This stage focuses on the formation of intellectual ability and social connections. Fixation is uncommon at the latency stage, though child may face social or emotional difficulties which affect interpersonal relationships and the ability to communicate socially in later life.

❖ **Genital stage:** - Last from adolescence and goes onto adulthood. It is marked by the reappearance of libido in a socially mature way with key emphasis on building healthy, adult relationships. Effective management of all former stages permits the individual to form intimate, responsible, and socially functional connections. Here, fixation can lead to interruption with intimacy, emotional regulation, and the ability to sustain healthy adult relationships.

Figure 4. Psychosexual Stages of Development

2. Psychosocial Theory Of Development: -

The Psychosocial theory of development was proposed by a prominent developmental psychologist Erik Erikson. This theory suggests that human development occurs through different psychosocial periods of life. Erikson underscored the role of social and environmental influences on personality and identity formation. His work spotlights the significance of social relationships and experiences in shaping identity together with psychological strength across the lifespan. During each stage of development, individuals deal with a unique psychosocial crisis that must be settled to develop a healthy personality and improved social relationships (Maree, 2021). Successful resolution of these crisis leads to the attainment of psychological virtues, while failure to resolve them may result in challenges in subsequent phases. The theory explains social development over a progression of 8 successive stages-

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- ❖ **Infancy (0–1 year)** - Grounded in the trust versus mistrust conflict, infants at this stage are totally dependent on caregivers for comfort and protection. When caregivers are attentive and responsible, the child develops a sense of trust in the world. If parents are neglectful or inconsistent, child develops mistrust which hampers their ability to establish and maintain interpersonal relationships in future.
- ❖ **Early Childhood (1–3 years)** -During early childhood, the child is preoccupied with the conflict of autonomy versus shame and doubt. They begin to claim autonomy through actions like as walking, eating food themselves, and making simple choices. Reinforcement from authority figures enables the child with autonomy and self-confidence, while over-criticism and restriction is likely to result in shame and doubt regarding their abilities in future.
- ❖ **Preschool (3–6 years)** – This stage is characterized by the crisis of initiative versus guilt. Here, children initiate exploration, organize activities, and engage with peers. When caregivers supports and motivates these initiatives, children cultivate a sense of purpose and self-confidence and if the child experience scolding or restriction for their efforts, it results in guilt and uncertainty in pursuing aims.
- ❖ **Middle Childhood (6–12 years)** - In Middle childhood the presented challenge is of industry versus inferiority. Achievement in academics, sports, and social communication assist them to develop a sense of accomplishment. Failure or lack of encouragement may lead to feelings of inferiority, having a negative effect on motivation and self-esteem of the child.
- ❖ **Adolescence (12–18 years)** – The most crucial developmental stage, it is renowned for conflict of identity versus role confusion. Adolescents reflect on the personal values and beliefs as well as goals of individual while also developing a sense of self. Positive resolution leads to establishment of a strong identity and purpose in life. Adolescence period provides a vital foundation for gaining insights into ways through adolescents construct their sense of self amidst modern time social pressures such as familial expectations and digital media influences (Dhabhai, 2025).
- ❖ **Adulthood (18–40 years)** – Adulthood is marked by the psychosocial crisis of intimacy versus isolation. Individuals attempt to form meaningful relationships and partnerships. Positive outcomes lead to loving and committed relationships, while failure may lead to social isolation and emotional distancing.
- ❖ **Middle Adulthood (40–65 years)** – In Middle adulthood the individual attends to the challenge of generosity versus stagnation. Adults centre their attention on contributing to society through work, or community involvement. Generosity leads to feeling of accomplishment and responsibility toward future, whereas stagnation may give rise to egocentrism and a sense of discontent.
- ❖ **Late Adulthood (65 years and above)** - This is the last stage of psychosocial development relating to the crisis of integrity versus despair. Individuals reflect on their lives and achievements. Integrity emerges when individual view life as meaningful, contributing to wisdom and satisfaction whereas despair arises when life is perceives as fruitless, giving rise to regret and dissatisfaction.

Figure 5. Psychosocial Stages of Development

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3. COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT THEORY-

The theory of Cognitive development was put forward by Jean Piaget who is renowned for his work on child cognitive development, he emphasized that children construct their understanding of the world through interaction, examination, and understanding. This cognitive development theory explains how children actively construct conceptual representations called schemas and evolve through four stages of cognitive development. This takes place through the process of assimilation and accommodation, enabling children to modify their thought patterns as they interact with their surroundings (Pakpahan and Saragih, 2022). This theory outlines the range of children's cognition through systematic stages. This theory involves following stages-

- ❖ **Sensorimotor Stage (Birth to 2 years):** - This stage of cognitive development where the infants learn to navigate the world mainly through their senses and motor actions. They gradually develop object permanence, understanding that objects continue to exist even when they are out of vision. This stage lays the foundation for purposeful actions and early problem-solving skills.
- ❖ **Preoperational Stage (2 to 7 years):** - Children in these stages start to use symbols, language, and imagination to represent objects and experiences. However, their thinking is egocentric, which means that they face difficulty in perceiving the perspectives of other people. They also struggle with mental operations such as conceptual understanding of conservation.
- ❖ **Concrete Operational Stage (7 to 11 years):** - During this stage, children acquire logical thinking skills in relation to actual events. They can carry out operations such as classification, sequences of objects, and conservation. Egocentric thinking reduces allowing them to perceive other's perspectives, though abstract thinking remains limited.
- ❖ **Formal Operational Stage (12 years and above):** - By this stage adolescents develop abstract thinking and the ability to reason as well as plan systematically. They engage in problem-solving, consider possibilities, and make use of deductive reasoning. This stage facilitates higher order thinking and the skills for scientific reasoning and moral judgment.

Figure 6. Stages of Cognitive Development

4. SOCIOCULTURAL THEORY OF DEVELOPMENT-

Sociocultural theory of development, was formulated by Lev Vygotsky, a Russian Psychologist. His theory focuses on the pivotal role of social interactions and culture in cognitive development. This theory suggests cognitive development is deeply rooted in social interactions and cultural learnings, with children acquiring higher mental operations through guided interactions with more knowledgeable others and cultural tools such as language (Marginson and Dang, 2016). Sociocultural theory recommends that human cognitive development is rooted in social interaction and cultural mediation (Alkurtehe & Dzakiria, 2018). This theory involves following key concept-

- ❖ **Interaction with others (IWO):** - Vygotsky strongly argued that cognitive development at its core is a social process. Learning begins through interaction with others before it becomes rooted within the child. They acquire knowledge, skills, and the ability to comprehend by collaborating, communicating, and receiving guidance from their surroundings.

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- ❖ **More Knowledgeable Other (MKO):** - MKO is defined as someone who holds more knowledge and experience than the beginner, which may include teachers, parents, or skilled peers. They play a critical role in assisting, supporting, and providing feedback which helps the child to accomplish tasks they cannot complete independently.
- ❖ **Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD):** - This is the area representing the difference between what a child can do on its own and the tasks that require assistance. Vygotsky argued that learning becomes effective when it takes place within the zone of proximal development.

Figure 7. Zone of Proximal Development

- ❖ **Scaffolding:** - Scaffolding is a temporary form of assistance provided according to the individual's needs. It is slowly reduced when the child gains independency to perform tasks which eventually lead to enhancement in the individual's performance.
- ❖ **Language in cognitive development (LCD):** - Vygotsky also stressed upon the significance of language in cognitive development. Language functions as the primary cultural tool through which children learn control over thinking, planning, and self-regulation of their behavior. By engaging in self-talk and adopting social dialogue, children develop higher-order cognitive functions such as problem-solving abilities. Together, these concepts explain Vygotsky's view learning as a socially determined and deeply rooted within cultural contexts, making the social environment an essential compound of cognitive independence.

5. Moral Development Theory-

Kohlberg established the Moral Development theory, which he built upon the work of Jean Piaget, suggesting that moral reasoning emerges through systematic stages, each representing a qualitatively different approach of thinking about ethical issues. Moral development in children remains confusing by cognitive reasoning alone wherefore other factors such as emotional control, quality of social relationships, and psychological needs contribute significantly to how moral judgment and behaviour develop (Keung, 2013). Moral development theory proposes that individual's progress through methodical levels and stages of moral reasoning from concrete ideas of right and wrong to principle of ethical thinking, this progress can explain how moral education should be designed at school level for better moral development of individual (Nainggolan and Naibaho, 2022). Kohlberg's theory is organized into three levels, each containing two stages-

- ❖ **The pre-conventional level:** - This level is a key part of childhood and is characterized by self-centred reasoning. At this level the stages of moral development are, stage one is the obedience and punishment orientation, explaining why children view rules as fixed and follow them to avoid negative consequences. Stage two is individualism and exchange in which children recognize that different individuals have different interests and may act in ways that serve their own needs.
- ❖ **The conventional level:** - This level is a key part of adolescence and adult. The individual begin to internalize moral standards. At this level the stages of moral development are, stage three is the good interpersonal relationships stage, which involves valuing trust, loyalty thus establishing and maintaining relationships. Stage four, is maintaining the social order stage which is prioritized by obeying laws, maintain a respectful attitude towards authority figures and fulfilling social obligations to maintain order.

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❖ **The post-conventional level:** - This level is achieved by some adults, but not all. Here the individual's develop the realisation of them as a separate entities from and their own principles may take over societal norms. At this level the stages of moral development are, stage five is the social contract and individual rights stage which focuses upon understanding laws based on social agreements which can be changed to promote human welfare. Stage six, is the universal ethical principles stage, which is noted for adopted principles of justice, equality, and human rights, which guide moral reasoning even if they are in conflict with laws or social norms.

Figure 8. Stages of Moral Development

Study conducted by Corradi, (2024) on psychosexual theory stated that early experiences and unconscious motivations have an impact on personality formation, any unresolved quarrel has the potential to cause fixation and influence conduct in the future. A study conducted by Maree, (2021b) on growth happens through a sequence of psychosocial phases stated that each of phases which involves a conflict, influences the creation of personality. It highlighted how social interaction and life events have a significant impact on identity development. Another study conducted by Wang & Wang, (2015) investigated the connection between learning processes and cognitive development according to this study, children actively create knowledge through directed learning, interaction, and observation. Another study by Shabani, (2016) based on Vygotsky's sociocultural theory stated that social interaction is the starting point for cognitive development, which is then internalized by the individual. It highlighted the function of social mediation, in which interaction with more experienced people facilitates learning. A study conducted by Morris, (2014) looked at moral growth in connection to Kohlberg's paradigm, according to the study, moral thinking goes through organized phases that are impacted by cognitive development. It highlighted how people transition from self-serving to morally upright reasoning.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed at explaining major theory and principles of child and adolescent development by conceptualizing development as a continuous, holistic and ongoing process. It analyses how physical, cognitive, emotional and social domains interact continuously to shape growth from early childhood through adolescence. The study also focuses on the major and important development principles to understand individual differences and patterns of variation this ongoing process of development. The study also highlights childhood as a critical period for acquiring important competencies, self- concept and emotional attachments whereas adolescence is described as a phase of identity formation, cognitive improvement and social reorientation. Major developmental theories were discussed like the psychosexual theory which says that development is the result of childhood conflicts, then the psychosocial theory which stated how individual develops across lifespan through social interaction in there developmental stages, then the cognitive development theory which describes how cognitive processes are evolved through lifespan of the individual, then the sociocultural theory which emphasizes on how culture practices influences development and then the moral development theory which explains how moral reasoning is develop in the individual. Reviewing these theories provide theoretical foundation which together provides perspective offering comprehensive understanding of how cultural, psychological and social factors collectively influence human development.

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CONCLUSION

The study facilitated a holistic comprehension of child and adolescent development by thoroughly synthesising core developmental principles and major theories of development. Development was accentuated as a continuous and life-long process impacted by the complex interaction of various psychological factors, environmental conditions, and social experiences. The study focused on development which occur across multiple domains such as physical, cognitive, emotional, social, and moral, which remain closely connected throughout different stages of life. Childhood was recognized as a period for acquiring essential skills, emotional regulation, and social understanding, while adolescence emerged as a critical phase for identity formation, cognitive maturity, and increasing autonomy.

IMPLICATIONS

This study is highly relevant in current scenario as child and adolescent develop in environments that go through rapid social, cultural, and digital changes. The development principles will help in the better understanding of individual differences and evolution during developmental processes. The developmental theories discussed in the study serves as a diagnostic map for the clinicians to identify the origin of various psychological dysfunction by tracking back there development stages and domains which allows them to treat the root cause rather than just the symptoms. Together the study provide an insight on how development is influenced by various factors and how an appropriate support can help the individual accomplish there maximum developmental potential.

REFERENCES

- 1) Semasinghe, W. M. (2020). *Development, what does it really mean?* *Acta Politica Polonica*, 49, 51–59. <https://doi.org/10.18276/ap.2020.49-05>
- 2) Chopik, W. J. (2022). A space-time theory of psychological development. *Current Research in Ecological and Social Psychology*, 4, 100085. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cresp.2022.100085>
- 3) Berk, L. (2015). *Child development*. Pearson Higher Education AU.
- 4) Yi, L. J., & Keat, O. B. (2024). An Overview of Child Development from the Theoretical Perspectives. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, (09). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v7-i09-56>
- 5) Steinberg, L., & Morris, A. S. (2001). Adolescent Development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 83–110. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.83>
- 6) Families, B. O. C. Y. A., Education, D. O. B. a. S. S. A., Division, H. a. M., & Medicine, N. a. O. S. E. A. (2019). The promise of adolescence. In National Academies Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25388>
- 7) Dodge, K. A. (2004). The Nature-Nurture Debate and public policy. *Merrill-Palmer Quarterly*, 50(4), 418–427. <https://doi.org/10.1353/mpq.2004.0028>
- 8) Sternberg, R. J., & Okagaki, L. (1989). *Continuity and Discontinuity in Intellectual Development Are Not a Matter of &Egr;ither-Or*. *Human Development*, 32(3–4), 158–166. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000276463>
- 9) Bornstein, M. H., Putnick, D. L., & Esposito, G. (2017). Continuity and stability in development. *Child Development Perspectives*, 11(2), 113–119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12221>
- 10) Infurna, F. J. (2021). Utilizing principles of Life-Span developmental psychology to study the complexities of resilience across the adult life span. *The Gerontologist*, 61(6), 807–818. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnab086>
- 11) Baltes, P. B., Staudinger, U. M., & Lindenberger, U. (1999). LIFESPAN PSYCHOLOGY: Theory and application to intellectual functioning. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 50(1), 471–507. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.50.1.471>
- 12) Black, M. M., Walker, S. P., Fernald, L. C. H., Andersen, C. T., DiGirolamo, A. M., Lu, C., McCoy, D. C., Fink, G., Shawar, Y. R., Shiffman, J., Devercelli, A. E., Wodon, Q. T., Vargas-Barón, E., & Grantham-McGregor, S. (2016). Early childhood development coming of age: science through the life course. *The Lancet*, 389(10064), 77–90. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(16\)31389-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(16)31389-7)
- 13) Prinzie, P., Amaranta, D. H., Belsky, J., & Bornstein, M. H. (2019). *Handbook of Parenting*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429433214>
- 14) Berliana, C. R. (2025). Exploring the depths of the psyche: the ID, ego, and superego in Jerry Spinelli's *Stargirl*. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15743123>
- 15) Elkataweh, H. H. (2013). Freud's Psycho-Sexual Stages of Development. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2364215>
- 16) Maree, J. G. (2021). The psychosocial development theory of Erik Erikson: critical overview. *Early Child Development and Care*, 191(7–8), 1107–1121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2020.1845163>

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- 17) Dhabhai, I. (2025). Psychosocial Challenges of Adolescents: Exploring Identity Crisis through Erikson's Theory. *RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 10(5), 322–328. <https://doi.org/10.31305/rrijm.2025.v10.n5.035>
- 18) Pakpahan, F. H., & Saragih, M. (2022). Theory of Cognitive Development by Jean Piaget. *Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 2(2), 55–60. <https://doi.org/10.52622/joal.v2i2.79>
- 19) Marginson, S., & Dang, T. K. A. (2016). Vygotsky's sociocultural theory in the context of globalization. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 37(1), 116–129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2016.1216827>
- 20) Alkurtehe, K. a. M., & Dzakiria, H. (2018). An overreview of the sociocultural theory and vocabulary development. *JEEES (Journal of English Educators Society)*, 3(1), 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.21070/jees.v3i1.1227>
- 21) Keung, H., MA. (2013). The Moral Development of the Child: an Integrated model. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 1, 57. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2013.00057>
- 22) Naingolan, M. M., & Naibaho, L. (2022). The Integration of Kohlberg Moral Development Theory with Education Character. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 31, 203–212. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v31i1.6417>
- 23) Corradi, R. B. (2024). Psychoanalytic contributions to Psychodynamic Psychiatry and Psychotherapy: Erik Erikson's Psychosocial Developmental Theory. *Psychodynamic Psychiatry*, 52(1), 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1521/pdps.2024.52.1.18>
- 24) Maree, J. G. (2021b). The Psychosocial Development Theory of Erik Erikson: Critical Overview. *Early Child Development and Care*, 191(7–8), 1107–1121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2020.1845163>
- 25) Wang, Z., & Wang, L. (2015). Cognitive Development: Child education. In Elsevier eBooks (pp. 38–42). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-097086-8.92007-5>
- 26) Shabani, K. (2016). Applications of Vygotsky's sociocultural approach for teachers' professional development. *Cogent Education*, 3(1), 1252177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2016.1252177>
- 27) Morris, W. (2014). The Earthly Paradise by William Morris. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315805399>